

Short name	EU CRCF	Long name	EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework
Geographical scope	EU member states (potentially non-EU projects might become eligible also)		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>The European Union (EU) is developing a regulatory framework for certifying carbon removal. Currently there are significant uncertainties regarding the scope, operation and ultimate use of this framework, which will likely prevail for several years as the instrument matures. Certificates are expected to be generated in a process similar to voluntary carbon market standards, but the EU commission will decide on project types and MRV methodologies.</p> <p>Project types included span three very different categories of carbon dioxide removal projects: 1) permanent removals involving geological storage, 2) removals involving durable storage in products, and 3) "carbon farming" removals. Categories 1 and 2 are relevant for CCU and CCS projects. It is imaginable that categories 1 and 2 might eventually become eligible for creating revenues from the EU ETS. The relevance of these credits to other EU climate policies, such as the Green Deal, EU ETS, ESR, LULUCF, Farm to Fork, and the circular economy, is also uncertain.</p> <p>It is unclear how "approved" credits under the CRCM will be differentiated from other voluntary carbon market credits.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework might become the most meaningful revenue source for operation of CCU/S projects in the long term • Fundamental uncertainties about the nature and operation of the framework during the coming years • Will the framework regulate all certification (even when done for voluntary carbon market transactions)? • What will be the demand for CRCF certified credits? • High transaction costs (with unclear added benefit compared to voluntary carbon market) • Unclear embedding in overall EU policy landscape 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MRV – complicates communication of what the different standards are and how their quality may be judged • Accounting – obfuscates the relationship between voluntary carbon markets and compliance efforts and their already complex relationship with national GHG inventory accounting 		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission (2023): Carbon Removal Certification, website landing page 		